

Yashil

IQTISODIYOT va TARAQQIYOT

Ijtimoiy, iqtisodiy, siyosiy, ilmiy, ommabop jurnal

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CENTRAL ASIAN TRANSPORTATION CORRIDORS: INDICATORS AND INTEGRATION ISSUES

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Abstract: Consideration is given to the issues and driving forces behind the transportation and communication integration of the Central Asian republics. Analysis is conducted on the development possibilities, benefits, and trends in the establishment of alternative transportation corridors. Trends in the degree of dependency between the transportation sectors of the states in the area are compared by year. The article presents an overview of the main transport corridors used by the Republic of Uzbekistan in the implementation of foreign trade operations. The article provides the factors of formation of new regional transport routes in the context of their impact on socio-economic development of the countries of the region and integration of world economic relations.

Key words: Transport corridors, transit, multimodal transportation, transport and logistics terminals, transport initiatives, regional transport system, railways.

Annotatsiya: Markaziy Osiyo respublikalarining transport-kommunikatsiya integratsiyasini ta'minlovchi masalalar va harakatlantiruvchi kuchlar ko'rib chiqiladi. Muqobil transport koridorlarini tashkil etishning rivojlanish imkoniyatlari, afzalliklari va tendentsiyalari tahlil qilinmoqda. Mintaqadagi shtatlarning transport tarmoqlari o'rtasidagi bog'liqlik darajasining tendentsiyalari yillar bo'yicha taqqoslanadi. Maqolada O'zbekiston Respublikasi tashqi savdo operatsiyalarini amalga oshirishda foydalaniladigan asosiy transport yo'laklari haqida umumiy ma'lumot berilgan. Maqolada mintaqa davlatlarining ijtimoiy-iqtisodiy rivojlanishiga va jahon iqtisodiy munosabatlarining integratsiyalashuviga ta'siri kontekstida yangi mintaqaviy transport yo'nalishlarini shakllantirish omillari ko'rsatilgan.

Kalit so'zlar: Transport koridorlari, tranzit, multimodal tashish, transport va logistika terminallari, transport tashabbuslari, mintaqaviy transport tizimi, temir yo'llar.

Аннотация: Рассмотрены проблемы и движущие силы транспортно-коммуникационной интеграции республик Центральной Азии. Проводится анализ возможностей развития, преимуществ и тенденций создания альтернативных транспортных коридоров. Тенденции степени зависимости между транспортными секторами государств региона сравниваются по годам. В статье представлен обзор основных транспортных коридоров, используемых Республикой Узбекистан при осуществлении внешнеторговых операций. В статье рассмотрены факторы формирования новых региональных транспортных маршрутов в контексте их влияния на социально-экономическое развитие стран региона и интеграцию мирохозяйственных связей.

Ключевые слова: Транспортные коридоры, транзит, мультимодальные перевозки, транспортно-логистические терминалы, транспортные инициативы, региональная транспортная система, железные дороги.

The history of economic development is, for the most part, a history of overcoming the obstacles created by the distances between trading partners.¹

INTRODUCTION

There are currently only 44 countries in the world that are landlocked.² However, there are 2 countries that are not only landlocked, but also bordering exclusively on countries that are also landlocked: Liechtenstein, surrounded by Switzerland and Austria, and Uzbekistan, surrounded by Afghanistan, Kazakhstan, Kyrgyzstan, Tajikistan and Turkmenistan.

1 Hill F., Geddie K. Siberian burden: the Failures of the Soviet planning and the future of Russia. Moscow, Scientific and educational forum on international relations Publ., 2007. 328 p.

2 List of Landlocked Developing Countries. Available at: <https://unctad.org/topic/landlocked-developing-countries/list-of-LLDCs>.

Numerous studies have clearly that countries located in the interior of continents, far away from seas continents, far from the seas and the world's major markets still face transportation and logistics constraints, which has a significant impact on the development of these countries.

It should be noted that apart from Europe, there is not a single successful highly developed landlocked country measured by the Human Development Index (HDI), and nine of the twelve countries with the lowest HDI indicators are landlocked. The landlocked European countries are an exception in terms of development outcomes due to their close integration with the regional European market. Landlocked countries that rely on transoceanic trade usually suffer from trade costs twice as high as their own sea neighbors. In landlocked countries, economic growth by 6% less than in landlocked countries, with other variables unchanged.³

For reference: *The Human Development Index (HDI) is an integral indicator calculated annually for cross-country comparison and measurement of living standards, literacy, education and longevity as the main characteristics of the human potential of the studied territory. It is a standard tool for general comparison of living standards of different countries and regions.*

The index has been published by the United Nations Development Programme in annual human development reports since 1990.

When calculating HDI, 3 types of indicators are taken into account:

Life expectancy - estimates longevity. **The literacy** rate of the country's population (the average number of years spent on education) and the **expected duration of education**.⁴

The standard of living, estimated in terms of Gross national income per capita at purchasing power parity (PPP) in US dollars.

If we explain the concept of HDI in our own words, then this index shows how well-fed, healthy, educated people can be in a particular country of the world and how developed their political rights and civil liberties are.

DISCUSSION

In the economic development of Central Asia, international transport operators are a vital element.

Today, more than 90% of freight traffic in intercontinental trade between Asia and Europe is carried out by sea. Landlocked developing countries spend about 18% of their export earnings on transport services, while developing countries spend 9% overall. According to UNCTAD, for Central Asian countries, transport costs in many cases reach 60% of the cost of imported goods.

According to FAO (Food and Agriculture Organization of the United Nations), many geographically landlocked countries face serious difficulties in achieving food security.

Almost a third of the world's landlocked developing countries are located in Europe and Central Asia. Many residents of these countries rely solely on agriculture for their livelihoods, but lack of access to the sea places an additional burden on agriculture and trade.

A study conducted by the World Bank notes that the cost of shipping imported Cargo from these developing countries is twice the cost of shipping their coastal neighbors.

Tariffs, border checkpoints and underdeveloped infrastructure lead to transport delays and further increase trade costs.

These costs are often passed on to consumers. The level of volatility of domestic food prices in these countries is three times higher than that of their coastal partners.⁵

The problems of the economic development of the inland developing countries are in the field of view of the United Nations.

"The international community has an obligation to extend a helping hand to countries far from the sea, to facilitate the access of their goods to world markets, as well as to provide them with technical and financial support in overcoming the problems associated with their geographical isolation." This was stated by UN Secretary-General Antonio Guterres, during his speech at the plenary session of the General Assembly in New York in December 2019. "The biggest obstacle on their way to international markets remains the high cost of transportation. Sometimes the transit costs of countries far from seaports are equal to 70 percent of export revenues," the UN chief noted.

"Let's join forces and help the 32 developing countries of the world that do not have access to achieve transformations and improve the standard of living of the population, the total number of which is 500 million," said the UN Secretary-General.⁶

3 Human Development Index (HDI). Available at: <https://hdr.undp.org/data-center/human-development-index#/indicies/HDI>.

4 Human Development Index (HDI). Available at: <https://hdr.undp.org/data-center/human-development-index#/indicies/HDI>.

5 Digging deeper into the arid terrain of the world's largest landlocked country. Available at: <https://www.fao.org/fao-stories/article/en/c/1457421/>

6 Achieving Sustainable Transport in Landlocked Developing Countries. Available at: https://www.un.org/ohrrls/sites/www.un.org.ohrrls/files/lldcs_publications/transport-in-lldc-report-final_june-22_2017_high.pdf.

It is obvious that for Uzbekistan, and for all other Central Asian countries, it is vital to have a well-branched and reliably functioning network of international transport corridors with access to sea and ocean ports, allowing the development of effective international cooperation in order to achieve sustainable socio-economic development.

In this context, Uzbekistan takes initiatives and supports all reasonable steps in this direction.

The country is actively promoting the launch and effective operation of the new China–Kyrgyzstan–Uzbekistan multimodal transport corridor, as well as the early implementation of the railway construction project along this route.

In addition, the Uzbek side supports practical cooperation on the development of the corridor “**Kazakhstan–Uzbekistan– Turkmenistan – Iran – Oman – India**”, created in accordance with the Ashgabat Agreement, which is currently the shortest route to reach the ports The Indian Ocean and the Persian Gulf.

Uzbekistan proposes to join forces in the formation of an integrated network of dry ports, logistics and wholesale distribution centers within the framework of the “One Belt, One Road” initiative, which will open up broad prospects for strengthening regional and interregional interconnectedness.

At the same time, much attention is being paid to the creation of new transport corridors connecting the railway systems of Central and South Asia.

In this regard, it is impossible not to note the agreements reached on the construction of the railway Mazar-I-Sharif - Kabul - Peshawar, which will not only connect promising markets of Central and South Asian countries in the shortest possible way, but also become a powerful platform in the context of stimulating the growth of national economies, regional and interregional trade.

Uzbekistan also supports the activation and full implementation of the provisions of the Main Multilateral Agreement on International Transport for the Development of the Europe-Caucasus-Asia corridor, that is, the TRACECA corridor.

The use of the Iranian port of Chahbahar in the future for subsequent access to the countries of Southeast Asia also has its benefits for Uzbekistan, this is its closer location compared to the port of Bandar Abbas, as well as the fact that this port has been withdrawn from American sanctions.

Taking into account the importance and relevance of the development of Central Asia as a single region, the head of Uzbekistan Sh.M. Mirziyoyev identified the main priorities of Uzbekistan’s foreign policy as conducting an active regional policy, creating a favorable political atmosphere in Central Asia, building constructive and mutually beneficial relations with the countries of the region in all areas, including in the field of transport.

It should be emphasized that the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan is almost at every international summit focuses on the need to develop coordinated approaches in the field of transport and transit, more active use of transport corridors, increasing their competitiveness, and improving overall transport connectivity in the region.

“Today, the Central Asian states face an important strategic task – to ensure the deep integration of our region into global economic, transport and transit corridors. In this regard, we propose to create a Regional Center for the development of transport and Communication Connectivity under the auspices of the United Nations”.⁷

“Increasing the transport and transit potential of our region is of strategic importance. It is important to ensure access through Central Asia to major world markets, including China, India, Pakistan and other Asian countries, as well as from Azerbaijan and Turkey to European countries. The development of transport corridors in these areas and the joint implementation of major projects to create a logistics infrastructure fully meet our common interests” – the President mentioned.

Uzbekistan stands for expanding the network of transport corridors and increasing the transit potential of our regions that contributes to an even greater intensification of economic cooperation. The country is interested in further development of Uzbekistan-Turkmenistan-Iran-Oman, Uzbekistan-Kyrgyzstan- China transport corridors, as well as routes providing access through Azerbaijan to Turkey and European countries. In addition, the construction of the new Mazar-I-Sharif–Kabul-Peshawar railway is of great importance for the integration of Afghanistan into Uzbekistan’s vast region and ensuring sustainable development.

“New prospects for all SCO countries are opening up initiatives to build transport corridors that will help Afghanistan regain its historical role as a connecting bridge between Central and South Asia”.⁸

“Speaking about the priorities of the expanding regional partnership, I would like to emphasize the following.

It is important to focus on the practical implementation of tasks in the trade, economic, investment, transport, communication and energy sectors. These are the priorities of dynamic development and ensuring the competitiveness of the entire region.

7 Speech by the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan H.E. Mr. Shavkat Mirziyoyev at the 75th Session of the United Nations General Assembly. Available at: <https://www.un.int/uzbekistan/news/speech-president-republic-uzbekistan-he-mr-shavkat-mirziyoyev-75th-session-united-nations>.

8 President Shavkat Mirziyoyev’s speech at the SCO videoconference summit. Available at: <https://president.uz/en/lists/view/3936>

In this regard, Uzbekistan proposed to hold the Central Asian Investment Forum and the first meeting of the chambers of commerce and industry of Central Asian countries, to accelerate the creation of the regional council for transport communications during the Consultative meeting of the heads of Central Asian states in Tashkent in 2019.

Thus, the development of transport corridors will undoubtedly give an impetus to the development of our region.

Whether we are talking about the creation and development of international or national transport corridors, their use will certainly contribute to the involvement of economic entities in the process, the establishment of export relations, and will have a beneficial effect on the accessibility of goods for transportation.

The famous French economist Jacques Attali in the book "A brief history of the future. The world in the coming 50 years" proves that states have always fought for trade routes and caravans to pass through their territory, since this not only helped the economy grow and enrich the population, but above all, turned the country into an active participant in regional or global trade, as well as into a center of historical and cultural civilizational and scientific-innovative development.⁹

Development of transport communications in Uzbekistan, located at the intersection of roads between the West and the East have always been considered a priority. Railway transport consistently occupies a leading position in the implementation of major domestic and interstate transportation of Uzbekistan, the country's economy depends on its reliable operation. The price is relatively low in relation to other modes of transport. The longer the distance for the cargo, the cheaper it will cost to deliver it.

Well-developed railway infrastructure, which allows you to deliver the transported cargo without delay, despite the climatic or weather conditions.

High security guarantees almost 100% safety of the cargo, with the help of satellite and computer monitoring systems, the route is fully tracked.

Safe containers are used for many products. The versatility of this type of transport lies in the fact that it is possible to transport various types of goods: bulk products, construction materials, bulky goods, heavy machinery and much more.

RESULTS

Until 1991, railway transport in Uzbekistan had no access to the southern, western and eastern international transport corridors. Only the northern direction was available. This limited communication not only with the outside world, but also within the country.

Since gaining independence three decades ago, Uzbekistan has begun to actively take measures to form reliable, economically profitable transport corridors necessary for our products to enter foreign markets, import products in demand on the domestic market, as well as develop transport and transit potential.

Over the past period, a lot of work has been done to form a modern road transport infrastructure, open new routes to world markets, and create modern transport communications connecting our country with other regions of the world.

Much attention was paid to the construction of railways and the creation of a unified railway network in Uzbekistan. The first step was the construction of the Navoi-Uchkuduk-Sultanovaistog-Nukus railway with a length of 700 km, as well as the only modern one in Central Asia a 681 m long combined railway-automobile bridge over the Amu Darya. Next, the Tashguzar - Baysun - Kumkurgan railway line was built with a length of 223 km, which allowed Uzbekistan to reduce the distance of freight and passenger transportation to 170 km and freed Uzbekistan from the need to pay for transit, on the contrary, to earn money on it.

In recent years, Uzbekistan has built a new railway network with a total length of more than 1,200 km, more than 3,800 km of roads have been modernized and reconstructed, and almost 1,100 km of railways have been electrified. As a result, the total length of railways covering all regions of our country amounted to 6,500 km. Currently facing Uzbekistan and other Central Asian countries.

Asia faces the challenges of ensuring free and affordable access to sea transportation, reducing the costs associated with crossing the state border.

Today, Uzbekistan carries out its foreign trade transportation along the following main international railway corridors:

Corridor 1 – transit through Kazakhstan and Russia to the ports of the Baltic States – Tallinn (Estonia), Klaipeda (Lithuania), Riga, Liepaja, Ventspils (Latvia), as well as transit through Kazakhstan to the Russian port Saint-Petersburg.

⁹ Attali, Jacques (2011). A Brief History of the Future: A Brave and Controversial Look at the Twenty-first Century. Page 54, Skyhorse Publishing Inc. ISBN 9781611450132.

Corridor 2 – transit through Kazakhstan, Russia, Ukraine or Belarus to the countries of the European Union through the border crossings Brest (Belarus) and Chop (Ukraine).

Corridor 3 – transit through Kazakhstan, Russia and Ukraine to the Black Sea port of Ilyichevsk (Ukraine), as well as transit through Kazakhstan to the Russian port of Novorossiysk.

Corridor 4 (TRACECA) – transit through Turkmenistan, Kazakhstan and Azerbaijan to the ports of the Black Sea (Poti, Batumi), the Mediterranean Sea (Mersin).

Corridor 5 – transit through Turkmenistan and Iran to the port of Bandar Abbas, located on the coast The Persian Gulf.

Corridor 6 – transit through Kazakhstan and China, using the Kazakh-Chinese border crossing (Dostyk/ Alalshankou) to Chinese eastern ports, as well as transit through Kazakhstan to the Russian far Eastern ports of Nakhodka, Vladivostok and others.

It should be noted that the existing transport corridors are currently not being used effectively enough and their infrastructure needs to be developed to increase cargo traffic. The leadership of the republic is actively looking for ways to take an important political and economic place in Asia. On the other hand, as well as the whole of Central Asia as a whole, Uzbekistan is located at the intersection of all the nodal land corridors in Eurasia connecting East and West. Whereas Kazakhstan has become the main territory in the Chinese initiative “By providing extensive opportunities for northern routes aimed at Europe, Uzbekistan is trying to use its advantages and become a regional transport hub on the southern borders, due to its proximity to Afghanistan.

Thus, after analyzing the geopolitical situation in Central Asia, it should be noted, that Uzbekistan is currently becoming one of the important links in the normalization of the situation in the Afghanistan and the strategic center of the Central Asian countries in the implementation of transport, logistics and other economic projects in the Asian region.

CONCLUSION

1. Central Asia is a region located far from sea routes and world trade centers. The formation of new efficient and reliable transport corridors providing access to world markets is becoming a prerequisite for sustainable economic growth in the Central Asian countries.

2. In the countries of Central Asia, there is an understanding of the need to increase the level of interaction in the transport and communication sphere. The existing problems are evidenced by the rating of the World Bank’s logistics infrastructure, which is compiled on the basis of a survey of representatives of the logistics sector. Businesses from 155 countries in terms of such indicators as: customs procedures, transport infrastructure, logistics services, monitoring of cargo movement, timely delivery, difficulties in delivering international goods.

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